

Acid Aquation of Mixed Chelate Complexes. Aquation of Glycinato- and α - and β -Alaninatoethylenebisbiguanidecobalt(III) Complexes

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Acid-catalysed aquation of three amino acid chelates of cobalt(III) has been investigated in order to study the influence of chelate size and ring pattern on the rates of reactions. The complex ion chosen is $\text{Co}(\text{EBB})(\text{am})^{2+}$, where EBB = ethylenebisbiguanide and am = glycinate (Gly), α -alaninate (α -Alan) and β -Alaninate (β -Alan). The observed pseudo-first order rate constant varies linearly with acid concentration. Only the cobalt(III) complex with β -Alan shows an acid-independent path as revealed from a plot of k_{obs} vs $[\text{H}^+]$. At 30°, the reactivity order of the complexes is : β -Alan < Gly < α -Alan. Activation parameters (ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger) have been determined in the usual way. Positive entropy of all the complexes indicates release of an 'am' chelate after the entry of solvent molecules in the coordination sphere.

Metal complexes having chelating ligands with basic sites interact with protons in acid solution to form protonated species. When more than one such chelating ligands are present in a complex, there is a possibility of protonation of all the ligands. However, the relative basicity of the chelating ligands will determine the priority order of protonation. In one of our earlier studies on acid-catalysed aquation of aminoacidobisbiguanidecobalt(III) complexes, it was observed that the aminoacido chelate undergoes dissociation with formation of *cis*-diaquabisbiguanide complex¹. Tetradentate ethylenebisbiguanide (henceforth called 'EBB') forms more stable complex than biguanide does²⁻⁴ and our objective in this case is to study how acid-catalysis of amino acid chelates takes place in presence of EBB and influences the removal of these ligands. Influence of ring size (5- and 6-member ring effect) and ring pattern (substitution on chelate ring) on rate may also be relevant here.

Results and Discussion

The observed first order rate constants of all the com-

TABLE 1—OBSERVED RATE CONSTANTS ($k \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$) OF AQUATION OF COMPLEXES

[Complex] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

	Temp.	[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)					
		0.01	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.08	0.10
Gly	22	3.51	5.30	7.36	10.87	16.30	20.0
	25	5.11	8.40	10.50	18.55	29.2	36.0
	30	7.67	12.0	17.91	28.14	49.0	59.5
	37	20.47	36.0	47.34	83.16	130.0	162.0
α -Alan	22	3.22	6.10	9.70	15.75	23.80	32.1
	25	4.50	9.72	13.91	24.04	39.02	47.00
	30	7.93	14.0	11.61	38.27	60.05	70.00
	37	12.45	25.11	39.20	64.20	104.5	130.0
β -Alan	30	2.81	3.20	4.01	6.52	5.80	6.80
	37	8.31	9.61	11.45	13.40	17.20	19.80
	45	21.49	26.50	30.70	43.29	59.0	70.0

plexes at different temperatures vary with acid concentration (Table 1). A plot of k_{obs} vs $[\text{H}^+]$ is linear for all the complexes having a positive slope. However, the glycinato and the α -alaninato complexes do not show any intercept but for the β -alaninato complex a positive intercept on rate axis is observed. The corresponding rate expression for the gly and α -Alan complexes may be given as

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k [\text{H}^+] \quad (1)$$

where, k is the second order rate constant for the acid-catalysed reaction. The values of second order rate constants as determined from the plots are given in Table 2. On the basis of the reaction products obtained and the first order dependence of rate on acid concentration, the mechanism of the reaction may be proposed as in Scheme 1.

where, am = anion of amino acids

Scheme 1

Similarly, on the basis of the reaction products obtained and dependence on acid concentration, the rate expression for the β -Alan complex may be given as

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_1 [\text{H}^+] + k_2 \quad (2)$$

where, k_1 is the rate constant for acid-dependent path and k_2 that for the acid-free path. The corresponding mechanism of reaction may be proposed as in Scheme 2.

The basicities of amino acids forming chelates as well as that of EBB as measured by their respective pK values at 25° are as follows : GlyH, 9.78; α -AlanH, 9.87; β -AlanH, 10.24; EBBH (pK_1), 11.85^{5,6}. Hence, EBB should be protonated before any of the amino acid anions and dissociate before any one of them. However, the reaction

product indicates the release of amino acid chelates only. Although pK_1 of EBB is higher than that of any of the amino acids, the other pK values (pK_2 , pK_3 and pK_4 are 11.3, 2.9 and 1.8 respectively) are much lower⁶. Protonation of the quadridentate EBB ligand induces a little strain on one of the chelate rings, but that is not sufficient to unwrap the multidentate ligand from the metal and dislodge it. It is also likely that hydration of amine group of the amino acid via hydrogen bonding between water and the amine ligands can cause partial solvation of ligands and facilitate their removal during aquation⁷. Such hydrogen-

Scheme 2

bonded interaction is not possible to the EBB molecule due to delocalized p -electrons surrounding the whole molecule.

Rate constant values (Table 1) show the general order of reactivities of the complexes as : $\beta\text{-Alan} < \text{Gly} < \alpha\text{-Alan}$. The glycinate and α -alaninate form five-membered chelate rings, but the higher rate of aquation of the α -alaninate complex is both due to the base strengthening character of methyl group with respect to hydrogen atom and a substitution of methyl group on a five-membered ring; both of these factors lead to a higher rate of aquation. Since α -alaninate is a stronger base than glycinate, protonation takes place more readily at α -alaninate chelate ring making its dissociation more facile. β -Alaninate forms a quasi-aromatic six-membered chelate ring; its quasi-aromatic character imparts extra stability and this chelate

TABLE 2—RATE CONSTANTS OF ACID-DEPENDENT AND ACID-FREE PATHS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Temp. °C	$10^3 k_1$ mol s ⁻¹	$10^3 k_2$ s ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Gly	22	2.00 ± 0.02		105 ± 4	57 ± 8.5
	25	3.50 ± 0.02			
	30	5.90 ± 0.04			
	37	16.20 ± 0.04			
α -Alan	22	3.00 ± 0.02		70 ± 4	50 ± 6
	25	4.60 ± 0.03			
	30	7.60 ± 0.02			
	37	13.02 ± 0.02			
β -Alan	30	2.10 ± 0.02	0.46 ± 0.01	130 ± 4	120 ± 14
	37	7.00 ± 0.20	1.28 ± 0.02		
	45	14.82 ± 0.35	5.52 ± 0.35	(100 ± 3.5) for acid-free path	(-4 ± 11) for acid-free path

Fig. 1. Spectra of complexes (concn., 0.001 mol dm⁻³) : (a) glycinate, (b) α -alaninate and (c) β -alaninate; (a1), (b1) and (c1) glycinate, α -alaninate and β -alaninate all in 0.05 mol dm⁻³ HClO₄, (1 d) aged, (d1) diaqua complex.

complex dissociates rather slowly in comparison to the other two.

Activation parameters (ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger) calculated by use of Eyring's equation from the temperature-dependencies of rate constant values of all the complexes are also summarized in Table 2. The ΔH^\ddagger values of all the complexes are high compared to other bisbiguanide complexes, and also by cobalt(III) standard. This indicates that EBB complexes are thermodynamically more stable than bisbiguanide and most of the cobalt(III) complexes. The entropy value of all the complexes by acid-catalysed path as given in Table 2, is positive showing that release of amino acid ligand takes place after the entry of solvent molecules in the transition state. For the acid-free path of the β -Alan complex, the entropy value is near zero. Thus in presence of a tetradentate ligand EBB, the five-membered amino acid chelates of Gly and α -Alan are more labile than the six-membered β -Alan chelate.

Experimental

Glycinatoethylenebisbiguanidecobalt(III) perchlorate : The complex sulfate was prepared by the reported method⁸. The corresponding perchlorate was prepared in solution whenever required by the metathesis of the complex sulfate with an equivalent amount of barium perchlorate.

α -Alaninato- and β -alaninatoethylenebisbiguanidecobalt(III) perchlorates : The complex sulfates were prepared according to literature procedure⁹ and the perchlorate salts were obtained as the glycinate complex.

Diaquaethylenebisbiguanidecobalt(III) perchlorate : Diammineethylenebisbiguanidecobalt(III) sulphate was prepared following the reported procedure¹⁰. It was dissolved in a minimum volume of water and treated with NaOH solution (0.01 mol dm⁻³) on a water-bath. When the evolution of ammonia ceases, the solution after neutralization, was concentrated on a rotary evaporator and allowed to crystallize. The crystals were washed with cold water and alcohol and dried in air.

The elemental analyses of the complexes (calculated values in parentheses) were found to be : [Co(EBB)-(Gly)](SO₄).1.5 H₂O : Co 11.9 (12.2), N 31.8 (31.9); SO₄ 19.6 (19.6) ; [Co(EBB)(α -Alan)]SO₄.2H₂O; Co 11.49 (11.69), N 30.21 (30.49), SO₄ 18.64 (18.60); [Co(EBB) (β -Alan)]SO₄.2H₂O : Co 11.4 (11.66), N 30.4 (30.49), SO₄ 18.45 (18.6); [Co(EBB)(H₂O)₂](ClO₄)₃ : Co 9.55 (9.50), N 23.01 (22.54), Cl 17.62 (17.15).

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Double-distilled water was used for making all the solutions. Kinetic runs were made in aqueous perchloric acid. Ionic concentration was maintained with sodium perchlorate. Experimental procedure has been described elsewhere¹. The spectra of 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ solutions of all the complexes, glycinato, α - and β -alaninato complexes are shown in Fig. 1. Fig. 1 also contains the spectra of all the complexes in presence of 5×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ perchloric acid after a day at 25° along with the spectrum of diaqua-ethylenebisbiguanide complex of the same concentration. The reactions were followed conveniently at 490 nm corresponding to maximum difference in absorbance between the reactants and the products. Pseudo-first order rate constants were evaluated in the usual manner.

Similarity of the final spectra of all the complexes with the spectrum of [Co(EBB)(H₂O)₂]³⁺ indicated that the diaqua complex is the final product of all the reactions with the release of amino acid. Amino acid was identified in the reaction mixture by the ninhydrin method¹¹. During the reaction, no isosbestic point appeared at any stage of the reaction. So the dissociation of the chelate ring was the only process taking place during the reaction.

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